

Incentives to airline-High Speed Rail cooperation under hub congestion: an antitrust perspective[§]

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Abstract

In this paper, we examine two forms of airline-High Speed Rail (HSR) agreements when operators jointly bear some lump investments to provide a bundle of domestic HSR and international air services through a multimodal congested hub. The first one is a vertical agreement (VA) where the HSR operator decides to sell a number of seats on the train to the airline, which, in turn, offers the combined rail-air service in the downstream connecting market. Under the second type of agreement, transport operators form a (supervised) joint venture (JV) that exclusively provides the combined rail-air service, while the airline and the HSR operator share the JV's profit on the basis of their relative bargaining power. Both types of agreements are beneficial to passenger traffic in the connecting market and in the overall network. However, when the air transport and the HSR service are sufficiently differentiated, or the hub capacity is sufficiently low, a VA between operators might increase congestion at the hub and reduce passenger surplus. Conversely, a JV agreement benefits passenger surplus regardless of the hub congestion and the level of substitutability between modes. However, such an agreement might not ensure incentive-compatibility when operators have significantly different bargaining power. Our findings provide antitrust authorities with some insights to decide whether or not intermodal agreements should pass antitrust scrutiny and/or whether to limit the scope of the cooperation in the presence of multimodal congested hubs.

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1. Introduction

The relationship between air transport and high-speed rail (hereafter, HSR) has a twofold nature. On the one hand, air transport and HSR can be substitutes on short-haul routes, where they compete head-to-head for passengers. On the other hand, they might be complements on long-haul routes served by connecting flights through a hub airport. If HSR is an effective substitute for either of these flights, then international connecting passengers might consider combining HSR with air service to move from origin to destination¹.

Among others, congestion at hub airports is one of the primary reasons for intermodal cooperation²: the airline can divert part of the short-haul traffic to the rail thereby making the relevant slots available for more profitable routes (Givoni and Banister, 2006)³. In turn, the HSR operator benefits from the cooperation insofar as it increases its load factor and market share on short-haul routes (Givoni and Dobruszkes, 2013).

Intermodal cooperation has significant welfare effects. On the one hand, intermodal agreements have an (obvious) positive impact on transport operators' profits. On the other hands, the effect on passengers' well-being (that is, on consumer surplus) cannot be predicted *a priori*. Cooperation between airlines and HSR operators increases product variety, but may raise competition concerns.

Despite the relevance of airline-HSR agreements, competition authorities have so far devoted little attention in investigating how airline-HSR agreements affect passengers. This can be partly explained in terms of the strong political support to such agreements (D'Alfonso *et al.*, 2015), but it is in stark contrast with the case of alliances between airlines, which have attracted significant antitrust scrutiny worldwide (see e.g., ECA, 2003; ICAO, 2013).

¹ A useful list of examples comprises partnerships subscribed in: (i) Asia, e.g., between China Railway High-Speed and China Eastern Airlines from Shanghai Hongqiao International Airport (China Eastern Air-Rail Service), Taiwan High Speed Rail and EVA Air/China Airlines/China Eastern Airlines from Taoyuan International, Taipei Songshan, Kaohsiung International and Taichung airports; (ii) United States, e.g., between Amtrak and United Airlines from Newark Liberty International Airport (Acela Express); (iii) Europe, e.g., between Deutsche Bahn and Lufthansa/American Airlines/Emirates from Frankfurt Airport (AIRail), Deutsche Bahn and Singapore Airlines from Dortmund Airport (Rail&Fly), Comboios de Portugal and TAP Portugal from Lisbon, Porto and Faro airports (Rail&Fly Portugal), Austrian Federal Railways ÖBB and Air Moldova from Vienna International Airport (Air & Rail Austria), SNCF and Air France from Paris Charles De Gaulle Airport (AIR&RAIL or TGVAir), Thalys and Air France from Brussels Midi Airport (AIR&RAIL), Swiss Federal Railways SBB and Swiss International Air Lines from Zurich Airport (Airtrain).

² Due to severe constraints to capacity expansion, airport slots are a scarce resource. The European Commission pursues the optimal allocation and use of slots to foster competition and improve quality of air transport services (EC, 2011). In this framework, Avenali *et al.* (2015) study an incentive pricing mechanism to manage effectively scarce capacity at congested hubs.

³ For instance, in the case of the AIRail Service provided by Lufthansa and Deutsche Bahn in Germany, multimodal transport passengers can use either flights or HSR services on the Frankfurt-Stuttgart route, while flights are no longer available on the Frankfurt-Cologne route.

We argue that the academic debate on airline-HSR cooperation still lacks maturity on two counts (the reader may refer to section 2 for a detailed review of the relevant literature).

First, at the present date none of the papers on the topic explicitly considers the formation of the air-rail partnership strategically. Indeed, these papers consider a full-scale cooperation scenario where the airline and the HSR operator maximize their joint profit over the whole network. Thus, in the analysis of the cooperation scenario, they do not distinguish between mergers and alliances, and they do not explicitly model transport operators' incentives to engage in the partnership. In reality, cooperation assumes very different forms from the extreme case of a merger. Transport operators have private incentives to engage in an intermodal agreement if and only if they expect to achieve benefits in excess of sunk costs. Indeed, airlines and HSR operators have different bargaining power when signing an intermodal agreement. Moreover, both airlines and HSR operators have to incur (possibly considerable) sunk costs to ensure compatibility, and thereby create complementarity, between transport services (Chiambaretto and Decker, 2012; EC, 2006). Otherwise, switching costs are perceived relatively high by passengers and the air-rail alternative is not conceived as a feasible alternative to the connecting flight.⁴ In this sense, complementarity derives from compatibility, and compatibility is a strategic decision⁵.

Second, the available results show that the welfare gains from cooperation are mainly driven by firms' profits, rather than consumer surplus. Therefore, the air-rail mergers considered in the above papers should be subject to antitrust investigation, particularly when the multimodal hub is capacity constrained.

In this paper, we fill these gaps. We shed light on the basic mechanisms that regulate the effects of intermodal cooperation on consumer surplus, depending on the interplay between some basic features of the hub-and-spoke transport network –the level of congestion at hub airports and the modal substitutability between air and HSR services– and the type of agreement. We also consider the role of the (sunk) costs borne to make cooperation effective and of operators' bargaining power in sharing air-rail profits.

⁴ Eurocontrol (2005) has pointed to a list of critical barriers to intermodal development. The main barriers are the following: “[...] investments needed for developing the intermodal infrastructure are very costly; in certain cases, actors' willingness for coordinating or collaborating is limited (because of, e.g., competition aspects); lack of information to passengers, concerning intermodal products; passengers' perception regarding rail transport is, in certain countries, relatively poor [...]”.

⁵ Interestingly, some attempts of cooperation have not found fulfillment, e.g., the 2008 Air France talks to Veolia Transport about a rail venture (Financial Times, 2008). Air France was looking at commissioning its own high-speed trains because it had been unhappy with the quality of rail-air connections when it had bought space on existing operators' trains (Financial Times, 2008). Within the venture, Veolia would have run trains under the Air France brand from the airline's hub at Paris's Charles de Gaulle airport to destinations across Europe.

For this purpose, we consider a representative hub-and-spoke network with one single-leg route (e.g., a short-haul route) operated by both an airline and a HSR operator, and an additional single-leg route (e.g., a specific international route) operated by the same airline in monopoly. The airline also operates the one-stop route composed of the two segments above, via a possibly congested (multimodal) hub airport. In this framework, the airline and the HSR operator decide whether to sign an intermodal agreement to provide a combined airline-HSR service in the connecting market through the hub.

We model two different forms of cooperation. According to the first type of agreement, the HSR operator decides to sell a number of seats on the train to the airline, and charges the airline for the transport service. Then, the airline commercializes the combined airline-HSR service and become a multiproduct monopolist. In doing so, the airline decides how many seats to buy on the HSR train and how much of this cost to include in the price of the entire multimodal trip. We can view this form of cooperation as a vertical agreement where the HSR operator provides the airline with a fundamental input. This is consistent with the stylized fact that we are not aware of any signed airline-HSR agreement involving direct coordination on the prices charged, while the case in which airlines usually buy space on existing operators' trains is not rare (Eurocontrol, 2005)⁶.

We then consider the case of a JV formed to provide the combined airline-HSR service in the connecting market through the multimodal hub. We assume that the combined airline-HSR service is the only source of profit for the JV. On the other hand, both the airline and the HSR operator collect profits from all services provided in the relevant markets, as well as a fraction of the JV's profit depending on their relative bargaining power. This gives rise to a generalized Nash equilibrium problem (GNEP) since the JV and the airline share the same capacity constraint. Formally introduced by Debreu (1952), GNEPs arise quite naturally from standard Nash Equilibrium Problems if the players share some common resource – a communication link, an electrical transmission line, a transportation link – or limitations – for example a common limit on the total pollution in a certain

⁶ The reader may refer to the AIR&RAIL intermodal agreement between Thalys and Air France. The intermodal product is handled by Air France only. It is included in the Air France booking system and made available to passengers that wish to travel from/to Brussels-Midi and Paris-Charles de Gaulle (CDG). The air carrier will forecast and confirm their traffic volumes to Thalys on an annual basis in order to determine the booking of one or two carriages per journey (first class, "comfort 1"). In addition, Air France has the possibility to book additional seats on an ad-hoc basis subject to availability on trains (e.g. in case of higher volumes of traffic than expected as it is the case with the booking of traveller groups). Thalys schedule of trains to/from CDG have been adapted to suit Air France departure/arrival timetables. Dedicated luggage hold are made available by Thalys to Air France passengers on Brussels – CDG trains. This is an exclusive facility for Air France passengers. Finally, at the Brussels check-in counter, Air France passengers gets the boarding cards for both the Brussels–CDG link and for the CDG–Air France destination flight. The ticketing aspect is thus integrated (Eurocontrol, 2005). The reader may refer to the same document for an interesting description of investments pursued by transport operators in the case of other intermodal agreements (AiRail and Rail&Fly) between Lufthansa and Deutsche Bahn.

area⁷. We interpret this scenario as a sort of ‘supervised’ horizontal agreement that aims at improving consumer surplus, while ensuring incentive-compatibility for firms. The rationale for this scenario derives from considering that airline-HSR agreements have several features in common with code-sharing agreements between airlines. We consider the case where the JV agreement passes antitrust scrutiny as long as firms cooperate for the sole purpose of introducing the new combined transport service for long-haul journeys through the multimodal hub.

We investigate the following issues: i) What are the main incentives for operators to sign the intermodal agreement?; ii) Under what conditions can the agreement improve consumer surplus and reduce congestion at the hub airport?; iii) How do passengers in the different markets share the overall impact of the agreement?; iv) Under what conditions does the agreement not materialize, in spite of being socially desirable?

Our findings show that both types of agreements are beneficial to the traffic in the connecting market and in the overall network. Indeed, despite the airline substitutes some feeding flights for feeding HSR rides in the connecting market, the capacity made available at the hub can be used to accommodate newly generated demand from product differentiation. However, congestion at the hub airport does not necessarily reduce. In fact, the beneficial effect due to the reduction of connecting flights may be offset by the overall traffic increase in the same market and, sometimes, in the single-leg markets. This is actually the case when the air transport and the HSR service are sufficiently differentiated, or the hub capacity is sufficiently low.

The vertical agreement can harm passenger surplus when air transport and HSR are perceived by passengers as sufficiently differentiated and the hub is congested. This occurs since HSR chooses the wholesale price of a seat on the train in order to induce the airline to shift capacity from single-leg markets to the international connecting market. In fact, with a first-mover advantage, the HSR can be rewarded with huge profit as long as the wholesale price of train seats is set strategically to increase its ridership.

Unfortunately, firms may decide to cooperate in the case whereby the vertical intermodal agreement is not socially desirable. Conversely, when the vertical agreement is socially desirable, there are cases where firms are not provided with sufficient incentives to cooperate.

⁷ Recently, GNEPs have seen gradually application in traffic and transportation field (Bassanini *et al.*, 2002; Altman and Wynter 2004; Zhou *et al.*, 2005; Sun and Gao, 2007). We extend this literature by considering that transport operators may decide to compete or cooperate for the use of the common resource.

On the other hand, the JV agreement increases the passenger surplus regardless of the hub congestion and the level of substitutability between air and HSR. However, the JV agreement might not ensure incentive-compatibility for firms independent of whether the hub is congested or not, depending on the profit under the outside option of no agreement and the operators' bargaining power in seizing a high share of the joint venture profit.

Our findings can effectively assist policy makers who have to decide whether or not such agreements pass antitrust scrutiny and/or whether to limit the scope of the cooperation in the presence of multimodal congested hubs.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses relevant literature. Section 3 develops the model and presents the benchmark scenario of no-agreement. Section 4 and 5 present findings for the two different types of agreements. Section 6 provides a discussion of results, insights to antitrust authorities and issues for further research.

2. Relevant literature

A burgeoning literature has explored airline-HSR competition. It mainly consists of empirical studies that analyse and predict mode choices between two cities or in a specific corridor (e.g., Park and Ha, 2006; Román *et al.*, 2014; Behrens and Pels, 2012; Fu *et al.*, 2014), or examine the impacts of HSR after a certain period of operation with aggregated market data (e.g., Dobruszkes, 2011; Fu *et al.*, 2012, 2014; Givoni and Dobruszkes, 2013; Albalade *et al.*, 2015). Some theoretical studies analyse the market equilibrium of airline-HSR competition with a game-theoretic approach including distinctive features of the two transport modes – gross benefit of travel, access time, in-vehicle time, expected schedule delay, value of time, modes' emissions heterogeneity (see e.g., Adler *et al.*, 2010, Yang and Zhang, 2012; D'Alfonso *et al.*, 2015). Recent contribution has investigated the long-term impact of airline-HSR competition studying how the market coverage and the network choice of an airline would respond to HSR competition on origin-destination trunk routes (Jiang and Zhang, 2016).

On the other hand, the academic literature on airline-HSR cooperation is still sparse. It focuses on air-rail mergers and their welfare effects, while neglecting the specific impact of airline-HSR agreements on consumer surplus. Within a hub-and-spoke network, Jiang and Zhang (2014) have found that cooperation improves social welfare when either the modal substitutability in the overlapping market is sufficiently low, so that the negative effect on competition in that market is small, or the hub capacity is tight, so that cooperation may alleviate congestion at the hub. However, cooperation increases consumer surplus only in the special case where the modal substitutability is very low and the hub is not capacity-constrained (so that passengers in the connecting market may

benefit from the increased traffic due to the combined long-haul airline–HSR service)⁸. Vertical differentiation between airline and HSR also plays a role. When hub capacity is tight, Xia and Zhang (2016a,b) have found that the airline will not necessarily withdraw first from the connecting market which occupies more airport capacity. Conversely, it will withdraw from the market in which it has less competitive advantage over HSR in terms of passengers’ valuation of the quality of the combined air-rail product. Intermodal cooperation benefits the (long-haul) non-stop market where only airline is present, but it harms the (short-haul) non-stop market where both airline and HSR are present. In the connecting market, intermodal competition should be encouraged only when the hub is not capacity-constrained.

Different from airline-HSR cooperation, the effects of ‘code-sharing’ alliances between airlines on consumers have been extensively investigated in the literature (for the case of international alliances, see e.g. Oum *et al.*, 1996; Brueckner and Whalen, 2000; Brueckner, 2001; Whalen, 2007; Jiang *et al.*, 2015). Generally, theory predicts that allowing cooperation between airlines in overlapping markets introduces a potential anticompetitive effect. Recently, Brueckner and Proost (2010) have studied the impact of imposing carve-outs on alliance partners. Interestingly, they find that a carve-out may be socially harmful when imposed on a joint venture (JV) alliance that involves full exploitation of economies of traffic density in overlapping markets (as under a true merger). In their model, alliance partners offer homogenous products and thus the welfare benefits of cooperation arise from the cost side. Under an airline-HSR agreement, operators provide differentiated products that may increase passenger traffic either in overlapping or in other adjacent markets. Thus, the welfare benefits of cooperation can be found on the demand side. This literature assesses the welfare effects of the partnerships in networks while generally ignoring the role of congestion at the hubs, which instead is an essential feature of our model.

Similarly, revenue sharing agreements between airports and airlines in vertical chains have been explored (Fu and Zhang, 2010; Zhang *et al.*, 2010)⁹. The degree of revenue sharing is affected by how the services of the airlines’ services are related to each other (complements, independent, or substitutes). In particular, when carriers provide strongly substitutable (complementary) services to

⁸ Jiang and Zhang (2014) build on a first attempt by Socorro and Vicens (2013) to evaluate the social and environmental benefits of airline-HSR integration. Socorro and Vicens (2013) show that such an integration is more likely to be beneficial for society if the hub airport is capacity constrained, when however the same integration may be detrimental for the environment. The main limitation of their model is that it does not endogenize the airline’s decision of allocating capacity to the different routes, depending on whether firms cooperate or not and on the level of hub congestion.

⁹ For extensive reviews on airport-airline agreements the reader may refer to Fu *et al.* (2011), Barbot *et al.* (2013) and D’Alfonso and Nastasi (2014). The reader may also refer to Barbot (2011), and D’Alfonso and Nastasi (2012) for welfare and competition analysis of contracts – other than revenue sharing – between uncongested airports and multiple airlines providing (only) substitutable services.

each other, the airport has incentive to charge airlines (to pay) airlines a share of revenue. In these situations, while revenue sharing improves profits, it reduces social welfare and negative effects on airlines competition may arise. These works examine the case of markets covered by non-stop flights between uncongested origin destination airports and abstract away from network effects, which instead is the case in our paper.

Our paper also refers to an emerging literature strand in the field of industrial organization on inter-firm bundling, where independent (single-product) firms may decide to sell their products in bundle (Gans and King, 2006; Armstrong, 2013; Brito and Vasconcelos, 2015).¹⁰ Typically, allied firms coordinate to sell bundled products at a discount relative to the headline prices set for separate product selling. Nonetheless, these papers show that bundled discounts yield negative welfare effects, particularly as to consumers. We extend this literature by considering that transport operators decide to compete or cooperate within a network structure. Generally, the operators' decisions on single markets (routes) in the network affect adjacent markets (routes) where they do not compete or cooperate. This is particularly the case for a hub-and-spoke network, where the airline's and the HSR operator's decisions on competition and/or cooperation affect the level of congestion at the multimodal hub.

A further relevant strand in the industrial organization literature concerns research and development (R&D) cooperation, and particularly the role and formation of JVs for R&D investment (d'Aspremont and Jacquemin, 1988; Kamien *et al.*, 1992; Yi and Shin, 2000). We share with this literature the idea that independent firms may have to coordinate their decisions to some extent to achieve innovation (that is, in our model, to introduce the new combined air-HSR service). However, in traditional models of R&D JVs, firms collect their profits only in the markets where they compete, which makes the case different from our framework.

3. The model

We consider the network of three nodes, i.e., cities, illustrated in Figure 1. An airline, *a*, operates the short-haul (e.g., domestic) route between city A and city H. On the same market, a HSR transport

¹⁰ In turn, these papers are related to the well-developed literature on product bundling by multi-product firms (Avenali *et al.*, 2013, discuss a list of relevant papers), and on product compatibility and systems competition, that is, competition between substitutes made of complements (see e.g. Matutes and Regibeau, 1988; Economides, 1989; Farrell *et al.*, 1998).

operator, r , offers a direct ride. The airline also serves two long-haul (e.g., international) routes, that is, market HB (with a direct connection) and market AB (with a one-stop trip).¹¹

Figure 1. Structure of the network.

City H can serve as a multimodal hub, because there is a HSR station at the airport. In principle, passengers travelling from city A to city B could transfer from A to H by HSR and then fly from H to B. However, since market AB is covered by a single-carrier service, we assume that multi-modal trips do not occur unless the airline and the HSR operator sign an intermodal agreement that gives rise to a new transportation product. For the agreement to become effective, each operator o , with $o = a, r$, has to incur a sunk cost F_o .¹²

An example of this setting is as follows. Node A is Nantes, Node H is Paris while Node B is Philipsburg (Saint Marteen). In the leg Nantes-Paris and Paris-Philipsburg Air France-KLM is a monopolist in the air transport market. Direct flights are offered from Nantes Atlantique Airport (NTE) to CDG and from CDG to Princess Juliana International Airport (SXM). However, SNCF direct rides are offered from Gare de Nantes (QJZ) to (CDG) by SNCF. In the market Nantes-Philipsburg, customers might book only two products. First, there is *TGV Air* product offered by Air France from QJZ to SXM via CDG. Second, there is a connecting flight offered by Air France/KLM offered from NTE to SXM via CDG¹³.

¹¹ We borrow from Jiang and Zhang (2014) the topology and market structure of the transport network.

¹² As a baseline, operators should enable passengers to purchase a single ticket for the entire multimodal trip. In such a case, the airline and the HSR operator decide to share the same trip, and each operator can mark each segment of the journey with its own code, independent of whether the airline or the HSR is actually operating the service. This requires operators to integrate their information technology and computer reservation systems. More importantly, it requires operators to coordinate schedules between air and HSR services. In doing so, operators decide to take the risk associated with possible delays on one segment of the journey, and provide passengers with proper warranties. Operators can also consider offering coordinated baggage handling (so that passengers should not care about baggage transfer at the intermediate stop), and/or supplementary services on HSR trains similar to those offered on short-haul flights (e.g., dining).

¹³ Taking off in NTE and landing in CDG or Paris Orly International Airport (ORY) by means of an Air France flight is the only option that is available for travellers who want a direct air journey. We note that flights from NTE to ORY are offered by HOP, which is the brand name of the regional flights operated by subsidiaries of Air France. HOP flights are operated by Airlinair, Brit Air and Régional under the HOP! brand. The new airline brand was created in 2013 to better compete with the low-cost airlines, which have taken a significant share of Air France's regional routes. Similarly, direct flights offered by Air France-KLM from Saint Martin to Europe are only available towards CDG and Amsterdam Schipol International Airport (AMS). We remark that Air France-KLM is the result of the merger in 2004 between Air France and KLM. Both Air France and KLM are members of the SkyTeam airline alliance.

Let define $M = \{AH, HB, AB\}$ the set of markets m , and $T = \{A, R, AA, AR\}$ the set of the transportation products t , where $t = A$ ($t = R$) stands for a direct flight (HSR ride), $t = AA$ stands for a connecting flight through hub H , and $t = AR$ stands for the multimodal trip through hub H . Let T_m be the set of transportation product available on market m . Given the transport network in Figure 1, we have: (i) $T_{AH} = \{A, R\}$; (ii) $T_{HB} = \{A\}$; (iii) $T_{AB} = \{AA\}$ when the airline and the HSR do not cooperate, and $T_{AB} = \{AA, AR\}$ when they sign an agreement.

Denote by q_m^t the quantity of seats offered by the airline and the HSR on product $t \in T_m$ in market $m \in M$. Previous assumption imply that there are 5 travel choices for consumers within the network. Passengers' preferences are described by the following strictly concave quadratic utility function:¹⁴

$$U(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_m \sum_t \alpha_m^t q_m^t - \frac{1}{2} \sum_m \left(\sum_t \theta_m^t q_m^t{}^2 + 2\gamma \prod_t q_m^t \right) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{q} is the vector of quantities q_m^t , with $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 5}$ if transport modes sign an agreement and $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 4}$ otherwise. The parameter $\theta_m^t > 0$ measures – for a given value of γ – the own price sensitivity of the demand function for the transportation product $t \in T_m$ in market $m \in M$. The larger θ_m^t , the smaller is the own price sensitivity. Moreover, we assume that $\theta_m^t = 1 \forall m \in M, \forall t \in T_m$. The parameter $0 < \gamma < 1$, measures the degree of substitutability between transport modes. The lower γ , the higher the degree of horizontal differentiation between the two products (i.e., the lower the substitutability). For simplicity, we assume that modal substitutability is the same in each market, and that it is independent of the type of intermodal agreement.

The parameter $\alpha_m^t \geq 0$ measures the highest willingness to pay for the transportation product $t \in T_m$ in market $m \in M$ and is a proxy of quality in a vertical sense. Dimensions such as reliability, punctuality, safety, on board comfort, customer service (EC, 2006) or cultural/personal mode preferences (IATA, 2003) may contribute to define service quality in a vertical sense. We assume that $\alpha_{AH}^t = \alpha_{HB}^t = \alpha$, whereas $\alpha_{AB}^t = 2\alpha$, where $\alpha > 0$. Thus, for simplicity, we abstract away from vertical differentiation between transport modes in each city-pair market. On the other hand, passengers have a higher maximum willingness to pay (wtp) for the long-distance travel AB than for the direct trips from A to H or from H to B.¹⁵

¹⁴ Quadratic utility functions have been used, among others, by Dixit (1979) and Singh and Vives (1984). Then, they have been extensively employed in the literature on inter-modality between air transport and HSR (see e.g. D'Alfonso *et al.*, 2015, 2016; Jiang and Zhang, 2014, 2016; Socorro and Vicens, 2013).

¹⁵ Qualitative results would not be affected if the maximum wtp of consumers were assumed to be equal to α in all markets as in Jiang and Zhang (2014).

If p_m^t is the price charged for product $t \in T_m$ in market $m \in M$, the utility function (1) yields the following inverse linear demands:

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{AH}^A &= \alpha - q_{AH}^A - \gamma q_{AH}^R \\
p_{AH}^R &= \alpha - q_{AH}^R - \gamma q_{AH}^A \\
p_{HB}^A &= \alpha - q_{HB}^A \\
p_{AB}^{AA} &= 2\alpha - q_{AB}^{AA} - \gamma q_{AB}^{AR} \\
p_{AB}^{AR} &= 2\alpha - q_{AB}^{AR} - \gamma q_{AB}^{AA}
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where consumers can purchase product AR only after an airline-HSR agreement.

We now turn to the supply side. Let Q_m^t the total number of product t in market m . For instance, Q_{HB}^A represents the total number of long-haul direct flights offered by the airline in market HB . It results $q_m^t = Q_m^t \times Size_m^t \times LF_m^t \forall m \in M, \forall t \in T_m$, where $Size_m^t$ and LF_m^t represent, respectively, the number of seats and the load factor of the vehicle used to operate the product t in market m by operator o . For the sake of tractability, for each product t in market m , we assume that the two modes operate under a fixed-proportions relation such that load factor is constant and the product between the size and load factor is constant (e.g., 100%) for both modes in all markets served. With fixed load factors and sizes, prices per seat, per traveler and per flight/HSR ride are equivalent and $q_m^t = Q_m^t \forall m \in M, \forall t \in T_m$. We assume that transport operators are profit-maximizing firms¹⁶. For analytical tractability, we abstract away from economies of traffic density and cost asymmetry between the two modes of transport. Thus, we assume that $C_m^t(q_m^t) = cq_m^t$ if $m = AH, HB$ and $C_{AB}^t(q_{AB}^t) = 2cq_{AB}^t$, where c is constant and, thus, normalized to zero.

We take the runway capacity $k > 0$ at the hub H as exogenously given. The parameter k might be seen as the maximum number of passengers that can be transferred through the hub airport H in a given slot (or set of identical slots). Thus, depending on traffic, the hub airport H may be congested. On the other hand, we abstract away from capacity constraints at the other transport infrastructures in cities A and B, so that congestion is not an issue either for airports in A and B (e.g., they are peripheral airports) or for HSR platform in A.

¹⁶ The HSR operator may also take into account other objectives. Indeed, in some cases, HSR operators are owned by the government or, even if they are private companies, like in Europe, the networks are often co-invested by public administrations due to the huge capital requirements. In this paper, we follow Adler et al. (2010), Socorro and Vicens (2013), Jiang and Zhang (2014), Xia and Zhang (2016a,b) in that HSR maximizes profit. The reader may refer to Yang and Zhang (2012) and D'Alfonso et al. (2015) for the case in which HSR maximizes a weighted sum of its profit and social surplus.

Consumer surplus can be expressed as follows:

$$CS(\mathbf{q}) = U(\mathbf{q}) - p_{AH}^A q_{AH}^A - p_{AH}^R q_{AH}^R - p_{AB}^{AA} q_{AB}^{AA} - p_{HB}^A q_{HB}^A - p_{AB}^{AR} q_{AB}^{AR} \quad (3)$$

Alternatively, we decompose consumer surplus as follows:

$$CS(\mathbf{q}) = CS_{AH}(\mathbf{q}) + CS_{HB}(\mathbf{q}) + CS_{AB}(\mathbf{q}) \quad (4)$$

where subscripts denote relevant markets.

Adding transport operators' profits to (3), we obtain the following expression for social welfare:

$$SW(\mathbf{q}) = U(\mathbf{q}) - F_r - F_a \quad (5)$$

where $F_r = F_a = 0$.

In the benchmark case, transport operators do not sign any agreement. The airline is a monopolist in markets AB and HB and the airline and the HSR compete *à la Cournot* in market AH. We remark that quantity competition may be the more appropriate choice in case of limited capacities, even if firms are price setters. Cournot behavior has been assumed in Socorro and Vicens (2013), Jiang and Zhang (2014), D'Alfonso *et al.* (2015), Xia and Zhang (2016a,b). The decision problems for operators o are described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{q_{AH}^R} \pi_r(\mathbf{q}) &= p_{AH}^R q_{AH}^R \\ \max_{q_{AH}^A, q_{HB}^A, q_{AB}^{AA}} \pi_a(\mathbf{q}) &= p_{AH}^A q_{AH}^A + p_{AB}^{AA} q_{AB}^{AA} + p_{HB}^A q_{HB}^A \\ \text{s. t. } q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} &\leq k \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

We derive the equilibria of this scenario in Appendix A and we denote them by $\mathbf{q}^{NA} = (q_{AH}^{A,NA}, q_{HB}^{A,NA}, q_{AB}^{AA,NA}, q_{AH}^{R,NA})$, where the label *NA* stands for *no agreement*. In addition, we refer to the regions where the quantities are positive¹⁷ and denote by $\Omega_{NA,i}$ the constellation of parameters (α, γ, k) where the capacity constraint is not strictly binding at the equilibrium (subscript *i* stands for *interior* solution), and with $\Omega_{NA,b}$ the constellation of parameters (α, γ, k) such that the constraints is strictly binding (subscript *b* stands for *boundary* solution). We label the airport *congested* when $(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \Omega_{NA,b}$ and *not congested* otherwise.

4. Vertical agreement

¹⁷ This is the case for the solutions of each decision problem in the paper.

Under a *vertical agreement*, the HSR operator agrees to sell seats on the train to the airline. Let w be the per seat wholesale price charged by the HSR to the airlines. Previous assumptions on the number of seats and the load factor of transport operators imply that per-seat and per-traveler wholesale price are equivalent. Then, the airline commercializes the combined airline-HSR service in market AB and decides how many seats to buy on the HSR train. We remark that, in this framework, market structure changes. While the airline and the HSR compete on the short-haul market, the airline becomes a multiproduct monopolist in the long-haul market.

The timing of the game is as follows. At the first stage, operators decide whether to sign a vertical agreement (thereby incurring the relevant sunk costs to make services compatible, F_o with $o = a, r$) or not. In the case of agreement, at the second stage the HSR operator sets the wholesale price w . At the third stage, transport operators compete *à la Cournot*.

At the third stage, for a given input charge w , operators decide the number of seats to supply in the relevant markets:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{q_{AH}^R} \pi_r(\mathbf{q}) &= p_{AH}^R q_{AH}^R + w q_{AB}^{AR} \\ \max_{q_{AH}^A, q_{HB}^A, q_{AB}^{AA}, q_{AB}^{AR}} \pi_a(\mathbf{q}) &= p_{AH}^A q_{AH}^A + p_{AB}^{AA} q_{AB}^{AA} + p_{HB}^A q_{HB}^A + (p_{AB}^{AR} - w) q_{AB}^{AR} \\ \text{s. t. } q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} + q_{AB}^{AR} &\leq k \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

We denote by $\mathbf{q}^{VA}(w) = (q_{AH}^{A,VA}(w), q_{HB}^{A,VA}(w), q_{AB}^{AA,VA}(w), q_{AB}^{AR,VA}(w), q_{AH}^{R,VA}(w))$ the subgame Nash equilibria of problem (7) provided in Appendix B.

First, we study the effects of the input charge w on passenger traffic on the transport network. If the hub capacity constraint is not binding, we find the intuitive result that a higher w causes higher retail prices and lower quantities in market AB. On the other hand, if the hub capacity constraint is binding, the input charge w affects traffic in all relevant markets. Remark 1 summarizes the result.

Remark 1. Assume that the capacity constraint is binding. At the subgame-Nash equilibrium, if the transport services are sufficiently homogeneous, i.e., $\gamma > 0.5$, the following results hold when w increases:

- (i) the number of one-stop flights supplied to the market AB increases and their price increases;
- (ii) the output of the airline on the market AH and on the market HB decreases and the air ticket price increases.

Conversely, if the transport services are sufficiently differentiated, i.e., $\gamma < 0.5$, the following results hold when w increases:

- (iii) *the number of one-stop flights supplied to the market AB increases and their price decreases;*
- (iv) *the output of the airline on the market AH and on the market HB increases and the air ticket price decreases.*

The remark suggests that, if the transport services are sufficiently homogeneous, as w grows the airline is induced to shift the mix of products supplied to the market AB towards q_{AB}^{AA} and the price of the one-stop flight increases with w as well. Consequently, when w grows, the airline reduces the number of flights supplied to the markets AH and HB to allocate more capacity to AB. Conversely, if the transport services are sufficiently differentiated, the price p_{AB}^{AA} decreases with q_{AB}^{AA} and the airline does not shift capacity from AH and HB to AB.

At the second stage, the HSR decides the level of the wholesale price per seat, w , taking into account the impact it will have on the quantities supplied:

$$\max_w \pi_r(\mathbf{q}^{VA}(w)) = p_{AH}^R q_{AH}^{R,VA}(w) + w q_{AB}^{AR,VA}(w) \quad (8)$$

Let w^{VA} denote the solution to problem (8) (see Appendix B) and $\mathbf{q}^{VA} = \mathbf{q}^{VA}(w^{VA})$. We denote by $\Omega_{VA,i}$ the constellation of parameters (α, γ, k) such that the capacity constraint is not strictly binding at the equilibrium, and with $\Omega_{VA,b}$ the constellation of parameters (α, γ, k) such that the constraint is strictly binding. Furthermore, we label the hub airport *congested* when $(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \Omega_{VA,b}$ and *not congested* otherwise.

Remark 2. *At the equilibrium, the HSR operator sets an input charge w^{VA} that is lower than the retail price $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$ of the train ticket if and only if one of the following conditions holds:*

- (i) *The hub airport is not congested and $\gamma > 1/2(\sqrt{5} - 1) (\cong 0.62)$.*
- (ii) *The hub airport is congested, $\gamma > \tilde{\gamma} (\cong 0.63)$ and $\alpha/k > \tilde{A}$.¹⁸*

It is easy to see that, when the hub is not congested, both w^{VA} and $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$ decrease as transport products become increasingly substitutes, i.e., as γ grows. However $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$ is less responsive than w^{VA} since the HSR keeps w^{VA} relatively low (compared to $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$) to limit the incentive of the airline to reduce q_{AB}^{AR} . On the other hand, when the hub airport is congested, γ also shapes the effect that marginal changes of w have on the allocation of the capacity of the hub to the markets (see Remark 1). Overall, the effect of γ on w^{VA} and $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$ is ambiguous. However it is easy to prove that when α grows $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$

¹⁸ For simplicity, we omit the expression of \tilde{A} , since it is quite complicated. Throughout the paper, for the same reason we will omit the expressions of some critical levels of k . All of these thresholds are available from the authors on request.

increases faster than w^{VA} and that, if $\gamma > \tilde{\gamma} (\cong 0.63)$, when k increases w^{VA} increases but $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$ decreases.

Remark 3. *At the equilibrium, the input charge w^{VA} is increasing in k , i.e., $\partial w^{VA} / \partial k > 0$ if and only if $\gamma < 1/2$.*

This result, together with Remark 1, suggests that, as the available runway capacity k grows, the HSR operator adjusts w^{VA} to induce the airline to reduce the number of flights supplied to the markets AH and HB. This means that, if transport services are sufficiently differentiated (i.e. $\gamma < 1/2$), the HSR operator increases w^{VA} with hub capacity. Conversely, if transport services are sufficiently homogeneous (i.e. $\gamma > 1/2$), the HSR operator decreases w^{VA} with hub capacity (even though this strategy reduces $q_{AB}^{AR,VA}$).

4.1. Consumer surplus and social welfare

In Lemma 1 we compare passenger traffic flows with and without the vertical agreement.

Lemma 1. *Compared to the scenario in which there is not a vertical agreement between the airline and the HSR, if the airline supplies a combined air-rail product to the market AB:*

- (i) *the total (air and air-rail) traffic in the AB market increases, i.e., $q_{AB}^{AR,VA} + q_{AB}^{AA,VA} > q_{AB}^{AA,NA}$;*
- (ii) *the total (air and rail) traffic in the network increases, i.e., $q_{AH}^{A,VA} + q_{AH}^{R,VA} + q_{HB}^{A,VA} + q_{AB}^{AR,VA} + q_{AB}^{AA,VA} > q_{AH}^{A,NA} + q_{AH}^{R,NA} + q_{HB}^{A,NA} + q_{AB}^{AA,NA}$;*
- (iii) *the air traffic at the hub decreases, i.e., $q_{AH}^{A,VA} + q_{HB}^{A,VA} + q_{AB}^{AR,VA} + 2q_{AB}^{AA,VA} < q_{AH}^{A,NA} + q_{HB}^{A,NA} + 2q_{AB}^{AA,NA}$, if (and only if) $\gamma > 1/2$ and $k \geq \tilde{k}$.*

The rationale for result (i) is that, despite the airline substitutes some feeding flights for feeding HSR rides in the market AB (so that $q_{AB}^{AA,NA} > q_{AB}^{AA,VA}$), product differentiation expands the market AB. Result (ii) is driven by (i) and by the capacity made available at the hub by the introduction of the air-rail product.

Result (iii) suggests that the vertical agreement between the airline and the HSR operator does not necessarily reduce congestion at the hub airport. Even though the agreement allows the airline to substitute some feeding flights for feeding HSR rides to the market AB and thereby reduce congestion, this effect may be offset by the overall traffic increase in the same market (so that $2q_{AB}^{AA,NA} \leq q_{AB}^{AR,VA} + 2q_{AB}^{AA,VA}$) and, sometimes, in the markets AH and HB (for each region of parameters, Table 1 shows the effects of the agreement on quantities). This is actually the case when the air transport and the HSR service are sufficiently differentiated ($\gamma < 1/2$), or the hub capacity is sufficiently low ($k < \tilde{k}$). Intuitively, high levels of product differentiation significantly increase the

demand in market AB, while low values of k severely constrain the airline as to quantities supplied (relative to the ideal case of unlimited capacity).

===Table 1 about here===

We now turn to the analysis of consumer surplus and social welfare, $CS(\mathbf{q}^{VA})$ and $SW(\mathbf{q}^{VA})$ respectively.

Proposition 1 *Compared to the scenario in which there is not a vertical agreement between the airline and the HSR, when the airline supplies a combined air-rail product in the AB market*

- (i) *if the hub airport is not congested, the agreement is beneficial to consumer surplus;*
- (ii) *if the hub airport is congested, the agreement reduces consumer surplus when (and only when) $\gamma < \tilde{\gamma}_2 (\cong 0.33)$ and $\tilde{k}_1 < k < \tilde{k}_2$;*

To uncover the drivers of the result in Proposition 1, we refer to the information on traffic in Table 1. Moreover, according to (3) we decompose consumer surplus as follows: $CS(\mathbf{q}^{VA}) = CS_{AH}(\mathbf{q}^{VA}) + CS_{HB}(\mathbf{q}^{VA}) + CS_{AB}(\mathbf{q}^{VA})$. For each region of parameters, Table 2 shows the effects of the agreement on consumer surplus in each market.

The result (i) hinges on the weak increase of traffic in all markets that follows the agreement. In turn, this traffic effect comes from product differentiation on the market AB and, when the hub is congested before the partnership, from the opportunity to release slots at the hub through mode substitution.

To understand result (ii) we distinguish two cases. If the hub is congested after the agreement but it was not congested before (i.e., if hub capacity is relatively low), the supply of q_{AB}^{AR} harms passengers in the markets AH and HB (where traffic decreases and the prices increase). This happens because the HSR chooses w to induce the airline to divert flights from AH to AB (see Remark 1) and because the airline prefers allocating slots to the market AB, where the (maximum) wtp of passengers is twice that of the market AH (while q_{AH}^A and q_{AB}^{AR} use the same hub capacity). This effect weakens as α grows. On the other hand, if the hub is congested either before or after the agreement (i.e., if hub capacity is very low) the forces into play are the same, but the incentive to shift operations towards AH are increasing in k .

===Table 2 about here===

Proposition 2 studies the effect of the agreement on social welfare.

Proposition 2. *There exists $\hat{F}_o > 0, o = a, r$ such that, if $0 \leq F_a \leq \hat{F}_a$ and $0 \leq F_r \leq \hat{F}_r$, i.e., if the fixed costs of the agreement are sufficiently low, the social welfare increases under the VA compared to the case where the airline and the HSR operator do not sign any agreement.*

In other words, combining this result with Proposition 1 suggests that, when the modes of transport are sufficiently differentiated and the capacity of the hub airport is relative low, the consumer surplus decreases with the agreement because transport operators are able to absorb the surplus generated from product variety.

4.2. Formation of the agreement

At the first stage, the transport operators decide whether to sign the agreement.

Proposition 3. *There exists $\tilde{F}_o > 0, o = a, r$ such that if $0 \leq F_a \leq \tilde{F}_a$ and $0 \leq F_r \leq \tilde{F}_r$, i.e., if the fixed costs of the agreement are sufficiently low, transport operators find it profit-maximizing to sign the agreement.*

Intuitively product differentiation in the AB market always allows the transport operators to increase third-stage profits, thus the agreement fails only if the costs incurred to build the partnership are too high.

From the results of Propositions 1-3 we can infer that, when $\gamma > \tilde{\gamma}_2 (\cong 0.33)$, the agreement could fail even though it would be beneficial for consumers surplus and society. This happens when F_a and F_r are such that $0 \leq F_a \leq \tilde{F}_a < \hat{F}_a$ or $0 \leq F_r \leq \tilde{F}_r < \hat{F}_r$. On the other hand, when $\gamma < \tilde{\gamma}_2 (\cong 0.33)$, the agreement could be supplied to the market even though this harms consumers. This is the case when $\tilde{k}_1 < k < \tilde{k}_2$ and F_a and F_r are such that $0 \leq F_a \leq \hat{F}_a < \tilde{F}_a$ or $0 \leq F_r \leq \hat{F}_r < \tilde{F}_r$.

From an antitrust perspective, the findings of propositions 1 and 3 suggest that, in some cases, antitrust authorities shall ban VA between air transport and HSR. On the other hand, from Remark 2 we can infer a simple criterion that antitrust authorities could adopt to give the green light to air-rail VA (thereby avoiding costly investigations): if the tariff that the HSR charges to the partner airline for a seat on the train, i.e., w^{VA} , is lower than the retail price of a seat on the same train, i.e., $p_{AH}^{R,VA}$ the VA shall be allowed.

5. Joint venture agreement

In this section, we assume that the airline and the HSR operator consider whether to form a JV to provide the combined air-rail service in the connecting market through the multimodal hub (i.e., in market AB). The JV is formed to provide consumers with an integrated transport product that features global ticketing and seamless check-in services.

We assume that the JV, as a distinct organizational entity from transport operators, maximizes profit from the combined airline-HSR service alone. On the other hand, the airline (respectively, the HSR) maximizes profit from all services provided in the transport network, plus a fraction β (respectively, a fraction $1 - \beta$) of the JV profit. A possible interpretation is that the airline holds a percentage β of the shares of the JV while the HSR holds the remaining percentage. These percentages, in turn, can be related to the operators' bargaining power.

The timing of the game is as follows. At the first stage, transport operators decide whether to form the JV (thereby incurring the relevant sunk costs) or not. At the second stage, transport operators and (possibly) the JV compete *à la Cournot*. We solve the game backwards.

The no-agreement scenario is described in (6) and results are available in Appendix A. Conversely, under the JV agreement, three firms (i.e., the airline, the HSR operator and the JV) supply transport services in the network. Firms simultaneously solve the following decision problems:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max_{q_{AB}^{AR}} \pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) = p_{AB}^{AR} q_{AB}^{AR} \\
& \text{s. t. } q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} + q_{AB}^{AR} \leq k \\
& \max_{q_{AH}^R} \pi_r(\mathbf{q}) + (1 - \beta)\pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) = p_{AH}^R q_{AH}^R + (1 - \beta)\pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) \tag{9} \\
& \max_{q_{AH}^A, q_{HB}^A, q_{AB}^{AA}} \pi_a(\mathbf{q}) + \beta \pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) = p_{AH}^A q_{AH}^A + p_{AB}^{AA} q_{AB}^{AA} + p_{HB}^A q_{HB}^A + \beta \pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) \\
& \text{s. t. } q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} + q_{AB}^{AR} \leq k
\end{aligned}$$

where π_r and π_a are those described in (6). The JV and the airline share the same capacity constraint and this gives rise to a GNEP with infinite Nash equilibria¹⁹. We denote by $\mathbf{q}^{JA} = (q_{AH}^{A,JA}, q_{HB}^{A,JA}, q_{AB}^{AA,JA}, q_{AB}^{AR,JA}, q_{AH}^{R,JA})$ the solutions of (9), which are derived in Appendix C. In particular, we have selected the solution which guarantees the fulfillment of the following assumptions: (i) the JV's benefits from a marginal increase of the hub airport capacity is proportional to the airline's benefit; (ii) the airline would benefit from an increase of the hub capacity more than the JV. Superscript *JA* stands for joint venture agreement. We denote by $\Omega_{JA,i}$ the constellation of

¹⁹ See Facchinei and Kanzow (2007).

parameters (α, γ, k) such that the capacity constraint is not strictly binding at the equilibrium, and with $\Omega_{JA,b}$ the constellation of the boundary solution. Again, we label the hub airport *congested* when $(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \Omega_{JA,b}$ and *not congested* otherwise.

5.1. Consumer surplus and social welfare

We can now compare market outcomes with and without the JV agreement, in terms of passenger traffic, consumer surplus and social welfare. As to passenger traffic, qualitative results are the same as under a vertical agreement (see Lemma 1). They are summarized in the following lemma.

Lemma 2 *Compared to the case where the airline and the HSR operator are pure competitors, under the JV agreement:*

- (i) *the total (air and air-rail) traffic in the AB market increases;*
- (ii) *the total (air and rail) traffic in the network (weakly) increases;*
- (iii) *the air traffic at the hub airport decreases if and only if transport services are sufficiently homogeneous and the capacity available at the hub is sufficiently high, that is, $\gamma > 1/(1 + \beta)$ and $k \geq \tilde{k}_3$.*

The following proposition focuses on consumer surplus, $CS(q^{JA})$. It shows that, in our stylized model, the supervised JV agreement always improves consumer surplus relatively to the case of no agreement.

Proposition 4 *Consumer surplus is higher under the JV agreement than in the case where the airline and the HSR operator are pure competitors.*

This result is driven by market AB, where the market structure changes from a monopoly to a duopoly. Indeed, though the airline softens competition towards the JV as it manages to seize a larger share of the JV profits, the JV does never take into account the effect of her choices on the demand for the one-stop flight. This result is consistent with the view that the JV scenario can be interpreted as a sort of ‘supervised’ horizontal agreement that passes antitrust scrutiny as long as firms cooperate for the sole purpose of introducing the multimodal transport service in market AB.

It directly follows from Proposition 1 and in Proposition 4 that a supervised horizontal agreement, in the form of a JV alliance, benefits consumers more than a vertical agreement (when double marginalization is not avoided).

Consider now social welfare $SW(\mathbf{q}^{JA})$. We have shown in Proposition 4 that a JV agreement increases consumer surplus relatively to the case of no agreement. It easily follows that social welfare is also higher with than without the JV agreement (Proposition 5).

Proposition 5 *There exist $\check{F}_o > 0, o = a, r$ such that if $0 \leq F_a \leq \check{F}_a$ and $0 \leq F_r \leq \check{F}_r$, social welfare is higher under the JV agreement than in the case where the airline and the HSR operator are pure competitors.*

5.2. Formation of the agreement

In this section, we investigate whether and when transport operators find it profitable to form the JV alliance, thereby incurring the relevant sunk costs. Indeed, this is the operators' strategic decision at the first stage of the game. This requires comparing either firm's profit under the JV agreement with the same firm's profit under the outside option of no agreement. Formally, firm o decides to form the JV when $\pi_o(\mathbf{q}^{JA}) + \beta_o \pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}^{JA}) - F_t > \pi_t(\mathbf{q}^{NA})$, where $\beta_a = \beta$ and $\beta_r = 1 - \beta$, $0 < \beta < 1$. Thus, the outcome of such a comparison depends on the operator's sunk cost, on the one side, and bargaining power, on the other side. Proposition 6 summarizes the results.

Proposition 6 *Consider the case in which F_o is sufficiently small, i.e., $F_o \leq \bar{F}_o$, and the degree of substitutability between the transportation products is sufficiently high $\gamma > \tilde{\gamma}_3 (\cong 0.19)$:*

- (i) *if the hub airport is not congested in case of no agreement, i.e., $(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \Omega_{NA,i}$, the JA is signed only if the airline's share of the JV profits is sufficiently high. In other words, there exists $0 < \tilde{\beta} < 1$ such that the transport operators form the JV if and only if $\beta > \tilde{\beta}$*
- (ii) *if the hub airport is congested in case of no agreement, i.e., $(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \Omega_{NA,k}$, the JA is signed only if neither of the transport operators appropriate a high share of the JV profits. In other words, there exist $0 < \tilde{\beta}_1 < 1$ and $0 < \tilde{\beta}_2 < 1$ such that the transport operators form the JV if and only if $\tilde{\beta}_1 \leq \beta \leq \tilde{\beta}_2$.*

Intuitively, if the hub is not congested in case of no agreement, the supply of air-rail product in market AB does not affect the profit of the HSR in the AH market. Therefore, the HSR signs the agreement as long as the JV is profitable relative to the outside option. On the other hand, the airline signs the agreement if and only if her share β of the profits of the JV is able to compensate for the profit loss due to the higher competition in the AB market. Conversely, in the case of congestion, it is easy to prove that the airline (partially) allocates the slots released at the hub (i.e., $q_{AB}^{AA,NA} - q_{AB}^{AA,JA}$)

to the market AH. The result is that the HSR signs the agreement if and only if $1 - \beta$ is sufficiently high to cover the loss of profits in the market AH.²⁰

6. Concluding remarks

In the last decades, one of the main goals of the European Union has been promoting intermodality in the passenger transport sector. Several public interventions and private projects have been deployed to abate transaction costs for passengers related to switching from a transport mode to another one. These have concerned, for example, infrastructure renewals to implement interconnections between transport modes, integrated baggage handling systems, better coordination between arrivals and departures, and empowering competitiveness within single modes.

In this context, more and more often air transport and HSR are not simply considered as competitors, but also as complementary modes. In fact, hub capacity may play an important role in justifying cooperation between air transport and HSR when it is a scarce resource relative to market demand. The cooperation between airlines and HSR operators has been recently studied from an economic theoretical perspective to analyze welfare implications.

In this paper, we have contributed to this discussion on two main counts. First, we have taken into account the private incentives of the airline and the HSR operators to sign an intermodal agreement. In particular, under different assumptions on the form of the cooperation, we have investigated how the costs of the agreement, the degree of hub congestion, the modal substitutability between air and HSR services, and the bargaining power of transport operators in appropriating the benefits of the intermodal agreement may induce operators to sign the agreement. Second, we have studied when these forms of cooperation may be desirable from an antitrust perspective, that is, when the surplus of passengers can benefit from the cooperation.

In our model, the cooperation essentially consists of offering a new transport service to the end users of the international connecting market. This service bundles domestic HSR and international air services through the multimodal hub. Providing this new service requires the airline and the HSR operator to jointly bear some lump investments. On the one hand, we have considered an intermodal agreement where the HSR operator sells seats on the train to the airline, which is in charge of the new transport service in the international connecting market. On the other hand, we have studied the case in which the intermodal agreement is implemented through a joint venture, entirely owned by

²⁰ When $\gamma < \tilde{\gamma}_3 (\cong 0.19)$, if the capacity at the hub is sufficiently low, there exist Nash equilibria of the JV game such that the airline does not want to form the partnership. The details and the proofs are available from the authors.

the airline and HSR operator, which is allowed to only provide the new transport service in the international connecting market.

Our results have shown that the vertical agreement in some cases can harm the passenger surplus, particularly when air transport and HSR services are perceived by passengers as sufficiently differentiated. In fact, even if the total (air plus rail) traffic in the network increases, the retail prices in single-leg markets may significantly increase because the airline shifts capacity from these markets to the international connecting market.

Unfortunately, we have found that firms may decide to cooperate even in the case whereby the vertical intermodal agreement is not socially desirable. Thus, antitrust authorities shall investigate such agreements, at least when the HSR sells a seat on the train to the partner airline at a higher price than the retail price for a seat on the same train in the one-leg market. At the opposite extreme, we have also observed that there are cases where, despite the vertical agreement is socially desirable, firms are not provided with sufficient incentives to cooperate.

On the other hand, we have shown that the JV agreement is socially desirable as it increases the passenger surplus regardless of the hub congestion and the level of substitutability between air and HSR services. In this sense, the JV agreement can be interpreted as a form of supervised agreement that the antitrust authority could introduce to shape the cooperation between the two modes of transport. However, the JV agreement might not ensure incentive-compatibility for firms. For instance, when passengers perceive the modal substitutability between air and HSR services as low and there is no capacity scarcity at the hub, firms are able to achieve higher profits when they do not cooperate. Instead, when the air and HSR services are perceived as sufficiently homogeneous, transport operators' bargaining power plays an important role. In fact, if the hub capacity is not scarce without the agreement, firms are induced to sign the JV agreement if the airline's bargaining power is sufficiently high, while, in the case that the hub is congested, the agreement arises if neither of the firms appropriate a high share of the JV's profit.

We can thus conclude that, under congested hub airports, socially desirable JV agreements are more likely to occur between companies with similar market power, such as between air transport and HSR incumbents. Based on the results obtained, antitrust authorities should foster JV agreements between incumbents, whereas the supervised agreement would fail in the asymmetric case where one mode of transport faces a weak level of competition (i.e. there is a dominant firm) and the other mode faces strong competition.

The paper also raises some issues for further research. Our findings have been obtained by assuming competition between the airline and the HSR operator in the domestic market. However, being the

international connecting market served only by an incumbent airline, any passenger of the connecting international market must fly with the incumbent even when he opts for the new HSR-air service. The analysis could thus be extended by considering a model where a third competing firm offers an integrated HSR-air transport service in the international connecting market. This is particularly relevant due to freedom of the air: foreign airlines are usually excluded from, or seriously constrained in domestic routes. With the help of air-rail cooperation, these foreign airlines can significantly increase their market presence (Chiambaretto and Decker, 2012). For instance, this is the case of the Strasbourg-Paris-Dubai market, where TGV Air, between SNCF and Emirates, and AIR&RAIL, between SNCF and Air France, are available to passengers at the same time.

In addition, the competition model relies on a very simple network structure where the airline and the HSR operator are not symmetric in serving end users. An extension of the model could consider a more symmetric network structure with a new rail station and one more route operated only by the HSR firm (for symmetry, this new route should connect the new rail station with both the spoke airport and the close rail station of the domestic route).

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Appendix A – No-agreement

Karush Khun Tucher conditions yield the following equilibria²¹ for problem (6):

$$\begin{aligned}
 q^{NA} = \begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,NA} \\ q_{HB}^{A,NA} \\ q_{AB}^{AA,NA} \\ q_{AH}^{R,NA} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{cases} \begin{pmatrix} k - \frac{5\alpha}{2} + \frac{5(24\alpha - 2\alpha\gamma - 5\alpha\gamma^2 - 8k + 2\gamma^2k)}{2(24 - 5\gamma^2)} \\ \frac{\alpha}{2} - \frac{24\alpha - 2\alpha\gamma - 5\alpha\gamma^2 - 8k + 2\gamma^2k}{2(24 - 5\gamma^2)} \\ \alpha - \frac{24\alpha - 2\alpha\gamma - 5\alpha\gamma^2 - 8k + 2\gamma^2k}{24 - 5\gamma^2} \\ 0 \\ \frac{2(6\alpha - \gamma k)}{24 - 5\gamma^2} \\ \frac{\alpha}{2 + \gamma} \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } k \leq \frac{12\alpha + 5\alpha\gamma}{4 + 2\gamma} \\ \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\alpha}{2 + \gamma} \\ \frac{\alpha}{2} \\ \alpha \\ 0 \\ \alpha \\ \frac{\alpha}{2 + \gamma} \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } k > \frac{12\alpha + 5\alpha\gamma}{4 + 2\gamma} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

We define $\tilde{\Omega}_{NA,b} = \{(\alpha, \gamma, k): \alpha \geq 0, 0 < \gamma < 1, 0 < k \leq (12\alpha + 5\alpha\gamma)/(4 + 2\gamma)\}$ and $\tilde{\Omega}_{NA,i} = \{(\alpha, \gamma, k): \alpha \geq 0, 0 < \gamma < 1, k > (12\alpha + 5\alpha\gamma)/(4 + 2\gamma)\}$. Furthermore, in our analyses, we will refer to $\Omega_{VR,i} \equiv \tilde{\Omega}_{VR,i}$ and $\Omega_{VR,b} = \{(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \tilde{\Omega}_{VR,b}: \mathbf{q}^{NA,b} > 0\} = \{(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \tilde{\Omega}_{VR,b}: k > 5\alpha\gamma/4\}$.

²¹ It is straightforward to prove that the decision problems are strictly concave.

Appendix B – Vertical agreement

Karush Khun Tucher conditions yield the following subgame Nash equilibria²² for problem (7):

$$\mathbf{q}^{VA}(w) = \begin{cases} \begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,VA,i}(w) \\ q_{HB}^{A,VA,i}(w) \\ q_{AB}^{AA,VA,i}(w) \\ q_{AB}^{AR,VA,i}(w) \\ q_{AH}^{R,VA,i}(w) \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } \left(\gamma \leq \frac{1}{2}, \alpha \leq \bar{\alpha}, k \leq \bar{k} \right) \vee \\ & \left(\gamma > \frac{1}{2}, k \leq \bar{k} \right) \\ \begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,VA,b}(w) \\ q_{HB}^{A,VA,b}(w) \\ q_{AB}^{AA,VA,b}(w) \\ q_{AB}^{AR,VA,b}(w) \\ q_{AH}^{R,VA,b}(w) \end{pmatrix} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\alpha}{2 + \gamma} \\ \frac{\alpha}{2} \\ \frac{2\alpha - 2\alpha\gamma + \gamma w}{2(1 - \gamma^2)} \\ \frac{2\alpha - 2\alpha\gamma - w}{2(1 - \gamma^2)} \\ \frac{\alpha}{2 + \gamma} \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } \left(\gamma \leq \frac{1}{2}, \alpha \leq \bar{\alpha}, k \leq \bar{k} \right) \vee \\ & \left(\gamma > \frac{1}{2}, k \leq \bar{k} \right) \\ \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\alpha(\gamma(-2 + \gamma(4 + \gamma)) - 2) + 2(2k + w) - 4\gamma(\gamma k + w)}{28 + \gamma(-16 + \gamma(-14 + \gamma(4 + \gamma)))} \\ \frac{\alpha(\gamma(10 + \gamma - 4\gamma^2) - 4) + (\gamma - 2)(2 + \gamma)(2(\gamma^2 - 1)k + (2\gamma - 1)w)}{2(28 + \gamma(-16 + \gamma(-14 + \gamma(4 + \gamma))))} \\ \frac{\alpha(\gamma^3 - 8 - 4\gamma) + 8w + (\gamma - 2)(2(\gamma^2 - 4)k - \gamma(4 + \gamma)w)}{2(28 + \gamma(-16 + \gamma(-14 + \gamma(4 + \gamma))))} \\ \frac{\alpha(24 + (2 - 9\gamma)\gamma) + 2(\gamma - 2)(2 + \gamma)(2\gamma - 1)k + (5\gamma^2 - 24)w}{2(28 + \gamma(-16 + \gamma(-14 + \gamma(4 + \gamma))))} \\ \frac{\alpha(14 - \gamma(7 + 6\gamma)) + \gamma(2(\gamma^2 - 1)k + (2\gamma - 1)w)}{28 + \gamma(-16 + \gamma(-14 + \gamma(4 + \gamma)))} \end{pmatrix} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

(A.2)

where the superscripts “*i*” and “*b*” stand for *interior* and *boundary* solution, respectively, and

²² It is straightforward to prove that the decision problems are strictly concave.

$$\bar{\alpha} = (2w - 3\gamma w - 2\gamma^2 w)/(16 - 5\gamma - 10\gamma^2 - \gamma^3)$$

$$\bar{k} = (16\alpha - 5\alpha\gamma - 10\alpha\gamma^2 - \alpha\gamma^3 - 2w + 3\gamma w + 2\gamma^2 w)/(-4 - 2\gamma + 4\gamma^2 + 2\gamma^3).$$

In the first stage the HSR anticipates that, depending on the level of the input charge set, the quantities supplied in the second stage might be constrained by the runway capacity or not. We obtain the following equilibrium values for the input charge:

$$w^{VA} = \begin{cases} \alpha - \alpha\gamma & \text{if } (\gamma < \bar{\gamma}(\cong 0.38), k > \bar{k}_1) \vee \\ & (\gamma \geq \bar{\gamma}, k > \bar{k}_2) \\ \frac{(-1 + \gamma)(\alpha(16 + \gamma(11 + \gamma)) - 2(1 + \gamma)(2 + \gamma)k)}{(2 + \gamma)(-1 + 2\gamma)} & \gamma < \bar{\gamma}(\cong 0.38), \bar{k}_3 \leq k \leq \bar{k}_1 \\ \frac{\alpha(\gamma(384 + \gamma(480 + \gamma(-180 + \gamma(-110 + \gamma(34 + 9\gamma)))))) - 672}{2(-672 + \gamma(384 + \gamma(478 + \gamma(-184 + \gamma(-86 + 5\gamma(4 + \gamma))))))} + & \text{otherwise} \\ \frac{2(2\gamma - 1)(\gamma(64 + \gamma(80 + \gamma(-32 + \gamma(-14 + \gamma(4 + \gamma)))))) - 112)k}{2(-672 + \gamma(384 + \gamma(478 + \gamma(-184 + \gamma(-86 + 5\gamma(4 + \gamma))))))} & \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

For the sake of readability, we define $\tilde{\Omega}_{VR,i} = \{(\alpha, \gamma, k): (\gamma < \bar{\gamma}(\cong 0.38), k > \bar{k}_1) \vee (\gamma \geq \bar{\gamma}, k > \bar{k}_2)\}$, that is the region of parameters where the capacity constraint is not strictly binding at the equilibrium (*interior* solution), and $\tilde{\Omega}_{VR,b} = \Omega \setminus \tilde{\Omega}_{VR,i}$ where the capacity constraint is binding at the equilibrium (*boundary* solution). Furthermore in our analyses we will focus on the region of parameters where the quantities are non-negative, i.e., $\Omega_{VR,i} = \{(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \tilde{\Omega}_{VR,i}: \mathbf{q}^{VA,b} > 0\}$ and $\Omega_{VR,b} = \{(\alpha, \gamma, k) \in \tilde{\Omega}_{VR,b}: \mathbf{q}^{VA,i} > 0\}$.

Appendix C –JV agreement

In (9) the JV and the airline share the same capacity constraint and this gives rise to a GNEP. If we write the KKT necessary optimality conditions of the game (eq. (A.4)), it is easy to see that (9) has ∞^1 Nash equilibria (when the capacity constraint is binding we have 7 unknowns and 6 equations).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \nabla_{\mathbf{q}_A} \left(\pi_a(\mathbf{q}) + \beta \pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) - \lambda_A (q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} + q_{AB}^{AR} - k) \right) = 0 \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{q}_{AH}^R} \left(\pi_r(\mathbf{q}) + (1 - \beta) \pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) - \lambda_{JV} (q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} + q_{AB}^{AR} - k) \right) = 0 \\ \nabla_{q_{AB}^{AR}} \pi_{JV}(\mathbf{q}) = 0 \\ \lambda_A (q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} + q_{AB}^{AR} - k) = 0 \\ \lambda_{JV} (q_{AH}^A + q_{HB}^A + 2q_{AB}^{AA} + q_{AB}^{AR} - k) = 0 \\ \lambda_A \geq 0, \lambda_{JV} \geq 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

For analytical tractability we assume that $\lambda_{JV} = \mu \lambda_A$, $0 \leq \mu \leq 1$. In fact, we are assuming that (i) the JV's benefits from a marginal increase of the airport capacity is proportional to the airline's benefit; (ii) the airline would benefit from an increase of the airport capacity more than the JV.

The equilibria of the GNEP are:

$$\mathbf{q}^{JA} = \begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,JA} \\ q_{AH}^{A,JA} \\ q_{HB}^{A,JA} \\ q_{AB}^{AA,JA} \\ q_{AB}^{AR,JA} \\ q_{AB}^{R,JA} \\ q_{AH}^{R,JA} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{cases} \begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,JA,i} \\ q_{AH}^{A,JA,i} \\ q_{HB}^{A,JA,i} \\ q_{AB}^{AA,JA,i} \\ q_{AB}^{AR,JA,i} \\ q_{AB}^{R,HA,i} \\ q_{AH}^{R,HA,i} \end{pmatrix} & \text{if } k > \frac{\alpha(-64 + 4(-1 + 4\beta)\gamma + 4(4 + 3\beta)\gamma^2 + (1 + \beta)\gamma^3)}{2(2 + \gamma)(-4 + (1 + \beta)\gamma^2)} \\ \begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,JA,b} \\ q_{AH}^{A,JA,b} \\ q_{HB}^{A,JA,b} \\ q_{AB}^{AA,JA,b} \\ q_{AB}^{AR,JA,b} \\ q_{AB}^{R,JA,b} \\ q_{AH}^{R,JA,b} \end{pmatrix} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where

$$\begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,HA,i} \\ q_{AH}^{A,HA,i} \\ q_{HB}^{A,HA,i} \\ q_{AB}^{AA,HA,i} \\ q_{AB}^{AR,HA,i} \\ q_{AB}^{R,HA,i} \\ q_{AH}^{R,HA,i} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\alpha}{2+\gamma} \\ \frac{\gamma}{2} \\ \frac{2(2\alpha - \alpha\gamma - \alpha\beta\gamma)}{4 - \gamma^2 - \beta\gamma^2} \\ \frac{2(2\alpha - \alpha\gamma)}{4 - \gamma^2 - \beta\gamma^2} \\ \frac{\alpha}{2+\gamma} \end{pmatrix} \text{ and}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} q_{AH}^{A,JA,b} \\ q_{HB}^{A,JA,b} \\ q_{AB}^{AA,JA,b} \\ q_{AB}^{AR,JA,b} \\ q_{AH}^{R,JA,b} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-4(-4+(1+\beta)\gamma^2)k+\alpha(-16-4\gamma+16\beta\gamma+4\gamma^2+\gamma^3+\beta\gamma^3+4(-2+\gamma)(-1+\gamma+\beta\gamma)\mu)}{(1+\beta)\gamma^4+16(6+\mu)-4\gamma^2(7+2\beta+\mu)-16\gamma(1+\mu+\beta\mu)+4\gamma^3(1+\mu+\beta\mu)} \\ \frac{(\gamma^2-4)((1+\beta)\gamma^2-4)k+\alpha(8(\mu-2)-2\gamma^2(\mu-2)+(1+\beta)\gamma^3(2\mu-5)+4\gamma(5+4\beta-2(1+\beta)\mu))}{(1+\beta)\gamma^4+16(6+n)-4\gamma^2(7+2\beta+n)-16\gamma(1+n+\beta n)+4\gamma^3(1+n+\beta n)} \\ \frac{2\alpha(\gamma^2(4+\gamma)+\beta\gamma(\gamma^2-8)-4\gamma)-16-\alpha(\gamma-2)(8+8\gamma+\gamma^2+\beta\gamma(4+\gamma))n+2(\gamma^2-4)k((1+\beta)\gamma n-4)}{(1+\beta)\gamma^4+16(6+\mu)-4\gamma^2(7+2\beta+\mu)-16\gamma(1+\mu+\beta\mu)+4\gamma^3(1+\mu+\beta\mu)} \\ \frac{2(-2+\gamma)(-12\alpha(2+\gamma)+2(2+g)k(\gamma-\mu)+\alpha(12+5\gamma)\mu)}{(1+\beta)\gamma^4+16(6+\mu)-4\gamma^2(7+2\beta+\mu)-16\gamma(1+\mu+\beta\mu)+4\gamma^3(1+\mu+\beta\mu)} \\ \frac{2(-4+(1+\beta)\gamma^2)(-6\alpha+\gamma k)+4\alpha(-2+\gamma)(-1+\gamma+\beta\gamma)\mu}{(1+\beta)\gamma^4+16(6+\mu)-4\gamma^2(7+2\beta+\mu)-16\gamma(1+\mu+\beta\mu)+4\gamma^3(1+\mu+\beta\mu)} \end{pmatrix}$$

We denote with $\Omega_{JA,i}$ ($\Omega_{JA,b}$) the constellation of parameters (α, γ, n, k) such that the capacity constraint is not binding (is binding) at the equilibrium of (9) and $\mathbf{q}^{JA,i} > \mathbf{0}$ ($\mathbf{q}^{JA,b} > \mathbf{0}$).

List of tables

	$\Omega_{VA,i} \cap \Omega_{NA,i}$	$\Omega_{VA,i} \cap \Omega_{NA,b}$	$\Omega_{VA,b} \cap \Omega_{NA,b}$		$\Omega_{VA,b} \cap \Omega_{NA,i}$
			$\gamma < 0.5$	$\gamma > 0.5$	
$q_{AH}^{A,VA} - q_{AH}^{A,NA}$, $q_{HB}^{A,VA} - q_{HB}^{A,NA}$	=	>	<	>	<
$q_{AH}^{R,VA} - q_{AH}^{R,NA}$	=	<	>	<	>
$q_{AH}^{A,VA} + q_{AH}^{R,VA} - q_{AH}^{A,NA}$ $- q_{AH}^{R,NA}$	=	>	<	>	<
$q_{AB}^{AA,VA} - q_{AB}^{AA,NA}$	<	<	<	<	<
$q_{AB}^{AA,VA} + q_{AB}^{AR,VA}$ $- q_{AB}^{AA,NA}$ $- q_{AB}^{AR,NA}$	>	>	>	>	>

Table 1 Effects of the VA on quantities.

	$\Omega_{VA,i} \cap \Omega_{NA,i}$	$\Omega_{VA,i} \cap \Omega_{NA,b}$	$\Omega_{VA,b} \cap \Omega_{NA,b}$		$\Omega_{VA,b} \cap \Omega_{NA,i}$
			$\gamma < \tilde{\gamma}_3 (\cong 0.21)$ $k > \tilde{k}_1$	otherwise	
$CS_{AH}^{VA} - CS_{AH}^{NA}$	=	+	-	+	-
$CS_{HB}^{VA} - CS_{HB}^{NA}$	=	+	-	+	-
$CS_{AB}^{VA} - CS_{AB}^{NA}$	+	+	-	+	+

Table 2 Effects of the VA on CS.